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Configuring Transmission Thresholds in IIoT Alarm Scenarios for Energy-Efficient Event Reporting

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ABSTRACT Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) applications involve real-time monitoring, detection, and data analysis. However, the intermittent activity of IIoT devices and limited battery capacity pose critical challenges. This paper addresses these interconnected issues, focusing on extending the battery life of IIoT devices sensing events/alarms by minimizing the number of unnecessary transmissions. We propose a threshold-based transmission-decision policy based on the sensing quality and the network spatial deployment. We optimize the transmission thresholds using several approaches such as successive convex approximation, block coordinate descent methods, Voronoi diagrams, explainable machine learning, algorithms based on natural selection and social behavior, and Q -learning. Through numerical evaluation, we demonstrate significant performance enhancements in low-power IIoT environments, with Q -learning performing the best, while the block coordinate descending method performs the worst. We compare the proposed methods to a benchmark that assigns the same transmission threshold to all devices. In low-density scenarios, all proposed methods outperform the benchmark, while in high-density scenarios, only Voronoi-(i), K-nearest neighbors, and Q -learning show better performance. Power consumption is reduced by up to 95% in low-density scenarios compared to the benchmark and by 63% in high-density scenarios.

INDEX TERMS Alarm scenario, Industrial Internet of Things, machine learning, spatial correlation, transmission threshold.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) aims to connect Industry 4.0 and thus support predictive maintenance, asset tracking, smart manufacturing, energy management, environmental monitoring, health and safety monitoring, remote control, smart grid management, and agricultural automation [1]. These applications enhance efficiency, safety, and sustainability across several industries, *e.g.*, manufacturing, agriculture, energy, and logistics. Indeed, by incorporating intelligent attributes, including the utilization of real-time data and automation for process optimization and decision-making, IIoT networks allow cyber-physical systems to operate proactively and efficiently [2].

IIoT networks are steadily evolving, driving massive data collection, analysis, and exploitation for control and sensing [3]. Indeed, many of these networks may encompass a massive number of low-power IIoT devices (IIoTDs) with limited battery capacity. The sporadic activation of these IIoTDs presents significant challenges in coordinating their sensing and transmission operations, increasing the likelihood of missing important events and the risk of collisions when multiple IIoTDs sense the same event or transmit highly correlated information to the base station (BS). Addressing these coordination challenges is crucial in IIoT networks for improving energy efficiency and supporting latency-sensitive applications [4].

Notably, the spatial arrangement of nodes in an IIoT network significantly affects event detection accuracy and the effectiveness of alarm notifications. By strategically designing the transmission strategies of IIoTDs based on their spatial deployment, it is possible to expand the covered sensing area, reduce blind spots, and optimize data transmission, ultimately enhancing the overall energy efficiency of the network [5], [6]. This has received significant attention from the research community lately as discussed in the following.

A. State-of-the-Art

Clustering and data-driven techniques may be designed to exploit spatial IoT correlation information, hence optimize IIoTD sensing and transmission operation policies, improving system's event detection capabilities and energy efficiency [4], [6]–[15]. For instance, a clustering-based distributed learning solution for a medium access scheme is proposed in [4] to tackle the problem where a set of sensors may communicate a joint observation. In [7], the authors exploit spatial correlation between device activations to schedule channels more efficiently. A spatial clustering technique using energy- and coverage-aware clusters is introduced in [8], while [9] proposes a gray prediction-based clustering strategy to reduce data redundancy and balance power consumption. In several of these works, clustering is further enhanced with machine learning (ML) techniques to improve adaptability and decision-making. For example, the authors in [10] propose a security framework that correlates activity across space and time to detect correlated transmission using data mining and supervised ML, reaching 99% accuracy. In [6], a hierarchical clustering-based dynamic technique is developed to enhance energy efficiency and event detection in smart agriculture. Therein, spatially correlated sensor data is used within clustered structures and processed using ML-based predictions to enable adaptive and efficient IoT operation. In [11], the authors exploit data correlations between devices to develop a random forest-based predictor for energy optimization in solar-powered nodes, leading to a 14% reduction in prediction error. The authors in [12] develop a lightweight online micro-clustering technique for energy-efficient real-time processing of IIoT streams. This approach leverages temporal correlations in sensor data to reduce both computation and memory costs. In [13], a correlation-aware beamforming and routing is proposed, leveraging deep reinforcement learning (RL) to exploit spatial correlation and data redundancy in IoT data for efficient long-range transmissions. In [14], a statistical model is introduced for joint correlated sensor identification and channel estimation, utilizing the least absolute shrinkage and selection operator integrated with orthogonal matching pursuit. Additionally, the authors in [15] propose a predictive duty-cycling and wake-up strategy for energy-harvesting IoT networks, where spatial and temporal correlations in device activity are exploited to optimize energy.

Despite the previous IIoT-related research projects, key issues like scalability, resource efficiency, and energy efficiency still persist in the practical implementation of correlation-based strategies for event-driven systems. Notably, many existing studies focus on post-sensing strategies, such as data aggregation or transmission scheduling at the BS, often relying on centralized coordination after sensing has already occurred. While this reduces redundancy at the BS or edge and improves processing efficiency, it does not prevent energy waste at the source since multiple IIoTDs may still consume power detecting and transmitting overlapping observations, thereby accelerating their battery depletion [4]. In contrast, our work targets the sensing stage itself, optimizing transmission decision-making directly at the device level before any data is sent. Exploiting spatial correlation earlier in the decision pipeline can enable proactive energy savings and reduce unnecessary transmissions [15]. However, early-stage coordination presents a critical trade-off, if transmission suppression is too aggressive, it may lead to missed event detections when all nearby IIoTDs defer reporting. To avoid this, coordination mechanisms must carefully balance the competing goals of minimizing energy consumption and ensuring reliable event reporting. Managing this trade-off effectively at the sensing stage remains a challenging and relatively underexplored problem in practical IIoT deployments [15].

B. Contributions & Organization

In this paper, we focus on developing adaptive transmission strategies for IoTs based on sensing quality and spatial deployment to enhance energy efficiency and event reporting performance in an IIoT scenario. The trade-off between event detection efficiency and power consumption is posed as a complex design challenge, for which we derive computationally efficient solutions leveraging convex optimization tools. Specifically, the contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

- We propose that IIoTDs adopt threshold-based transmission decisions to optimize energy efficiency without compromising event detection reliability. The threshold configuration task is formulated as a constrained optimization problem that aims to minimize the expected power consumption across all IIoTDs, subject to an error constraint that accounts for both collision and miss-detection probabilities. The formulation captures spatial and temporal correlations among IIoTDs supporting eventual context-aware and efficient decision-making.
- We propose multiple solution strategies for the proposed optimization problem, including successive convex approximation (SCA), block coordinate descending (BCD), and several heuristic and data-driven solutions to configure the transmission thresholds. The latter solutions include Voronoi diagrams, explainable ML, and algorithms based on natural selection and social be-

FIGURE 1. Illustration of an IIoT network where a coordinator controls and collects information from $N = 55$ IIoTDs. The influence of an event on the surrounding IIoTDs is modeled by a probability activation function that decays with the distance from the event epicenter to the IIoTDs.

havior like genetic algorithm (GA) and particle swarm optimization (PSO).

- We reformulate the optimization problem as an RL challenge for online adaptability and model-free decision-making. We propose a Q -learning solution due to its ability to handle dynamic environments where traditional optimization techniques struggle, and where finding a solution is computationally expensive or infeasible.
- We evaluate the impact of the proposed threshold configuration strategies to demonstrate their potential for improving energy efficiency and scalability in IIoT environments. Our findings indicate that the RL-based approach performs the best, while the BCD-based approach performs the worst. Moreover, all the proposed methods outperform the benchmark, which uses the same transmission threshold for all the IIoTDs, for low-density scenarios, while they perform at least similarly to the benchmark for high-density scenarios. Power consumption is reduced by up to 95% for low-density scenarios and up to 63% for high-density scenarios.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the system model and event influence analysis. Section III formulates the optimization problem. The proposed convex optimization solutions are described in Section IV, while solutions based on heuristic and RL are proposed in Section V. Section VI and VII discuss the computational complexity and practical considerations for the proposed methods, respectively. Section VIII evaluates the proposed method through numerical simulations. Finally, we conclude the paper and list potential future work in Section IX. Table 1 lists the symbols used throughout this paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a rectangular network area, ξ , of dimensions $L \times H$, where a single coordinator/BS serves as the gateway for a set \mathcal{J} of N short-range IIoTDs as depicted in FIGURE 1.

TABLE 1. List of Symbols

Symbol	Description
$d_{i,j}$	Distance between i^{th} event and an IIoTD j at (x_j, y_j)
$r_{j,h}$	Distance between two IIoTDs at (x_j, y_j) and (x_h, y_h)
$\mathbb{E}(\cdot)$	Expected value operator
$f_X(\cdot), F_X(\cdot)$	PDF and CDF of random variable X
g	Maximum number of iterations for the algorithms
\mathcal{J}	Set of IIoTDs
M	Number of clusters in k -nearest neighbors
P	Transition probability from inactive to active state
$p(\cdot)$	Sensing power function
P_{col}	Collision probability
P_e	Error probability
P_{miss}	Miss-detection probability
$\Pr(A_j)$	Steady-state probability of IIoTD j^{th} being active
$\Pr(A_j A_h)$	Probability of IIoTD j^{th} active if IIoTD h^{th} is active
$Q(\cdot)$	Lookup Q -table
S	System space
(s, a)	State-action pair
$\mathcal{T}(\cdot)$	First-order Taylor serie approximation operator
$W(\cdot)$	Expected power consumption per IIoTD
α	Probability of event occurrence
β	Cardinality of population vector in GA
ξ	Network area
η	Control factor sensitivity for a given distance
δ	IIoTD transmission threshold vector
∇	First-order derivative operator
μ_1, μ_2	Balance utility/cost factors
γ_j	Energy efficiency factor of the j^{th} IIoTD
ρ_j	Collision effect factor of the j^{th} IIoTD
σ	Miss-detection factor
U	Cumulative discounted reward
ζ^τ	Discount factor at state τ
$r_{\tau+1}$	Reward at a next state $\tau + 1$
π	Policy employed within RL
ω_τ	Learning rate at state τ
ϵ	Non-stuck factor (random action factor)
$\mathcal{O}(\cdot)$	Big \mathcal{O} notation
Θ	Population size for GA and PSO
Ω	Voronoi distance

Probability distribution function (PDF), cumulative distribution function (CDF).

These IIoTDs aim to detect the triggering of events, such as a moving object in motion detection applications or a fire in a fire-alarm system. The IIoTD switches from idle (I) to active (A) when an alarm event is detected, signifying the need for data transmission to the coordinator. The active IIoTDs send packets to the coordinator, which controls all the information exchange within its cell [16]. For simplicity, we assume that all IIoTDs transmit with equal power. The time is slotted in transmission time intervals (TTIs). The IIoTDs report their sensing information in state A (active), while no traffic is generated in state I (idle). We assume that the

FIGURE 2. The sensing coverage of an example network deployment for a) (top left) $\eta = 1$ and 25 IIoTDs, b) (top right) $\eta = 1$ and 100 IIoTDs, c) (bottom left) $\eta = 0.1$ and 25 IIoTDs, and d) (bottom right) $\eta = 0.1$ and 100 IIoTDs. The activation probability quantifies the event detection coverage.

coordinator knows each IIoTD location and that each event occurs uniformly in the area with probability α in every TTI [17].

Let us define $p(d_{i,j})$ as a sensing power function that represents the impact of the i^{th} event, triggered with epicenter (x_i, y_i) , on the j^{th} IIoTD within the network area, in the two-dimensional Euclidean plane \mathbb{R}^2 . Here, $d_{i,j}$ indicates the distance separating them. Moreover, $p(d_{i,j}) \in [0, 1]$ is non-increasing to mimic a decaying influence of events as the distance $d_{i,j}$ increases. As an example, FIGURE 1 depicts the influence of an event epicenter on the surrounding IIoTDs. Potential functions to be used include exponential [16], [17], linear [18], piece-wise linear [19], [20], and power-law decay [18] for general scenarios, while step [21] or sigmoidal [18] functions may be used for more stringent scenarios like indoor setups. In this paper, we use an exponentially decreasing function, *i.e.*, $p(d_{i,j}) = e^{-\eta d_{i,j}}$ with $\eta > 0$.

Note that η directly influences network coverage, which is defined as the percentage of the network area that falls within the coverage radius of at least one IIoTD, as depicted in FIGURE 2. A higher η leads to smaller individual sensing areas for each IIoTD, which limits the portion of the network each IIoTD can monitor. Conversely, a lower η expands the network coverage while increasing the overlapping sensing areas, which is the portion covered by two or more IIoTDs simultaneously. As seen in FIGURE 2(a), the probability of detecting an event is low due to a significant miss-detection probability, with the IIoTD's sensing coverage being only 14.79% of the total network area. In contrast, FIGURE 2(d) shows spatial coverage approaching the total network area. However, increasing the coverage area results in larger overlapping regions, which is undesirable

since it raises collision probability and power consumption, ultimately contributing to the battery depletion of the IIoTDs. Specifically, in FIGURE 2(a), the overlapping area is only 1.09% of the total area, leading to multiple IIoD activations and increasing collision probability. In contrast, as the coverage area increases in FIGURES 2(b), 2(c), and 2(d), the overlapping area rises to 13.40%, 61.05%, and 91%, respectively. FIGURES 2(b) and 2(c) represent intermediate configurations with moderate sensing coverage of 46.90% and 86.62%, respectively, illustrating the trade-off between maximizing network coverage and minimizing sensing overlap. Increasing (decreasing) the network coverage, increases (decreases) the power consumption of the IIoTDs, but also increases the probability of collisions (miss-detections) within the network. Thus, designing the IIoTDs' coverage areas to minimize overlap while achieving the desired event detection capabilities can extend overall sensing coverage and improve the energy efficiency of the network.

III. OPTIMIZATION PROBLEM

In the considered IIoT setup, IIoTDs make observations or measurements, which can be used to estimate the probability of successful signal reception, defined here as $p(d_{i,j})$. This probability is typically inferred from historical data or real-time measurements, considering factors such as signal strength and the deployment of IIoTDs. Leveraging sensing signal probabilities, $p(d_{i,j})$, as a guide for transmission decisions holds promise for optimizing network efficiency. This accounts for the likelihood of successful signal reception at various distances, considering interference and IIoTD deployment.

We propose setting (and optimizing) a threshold for each IIoTD to decide when to transmit data. We denote δ_j as the transmission threshold of the j^{th} IIoTD. Then, the transmission probability for this j^{th} IIoTD is given by

$$\Pr(A_j) = \alpha \Pr(p(d_{i,j}) \geq \delta_j). \quad (1)$$

Specifically, if the estimated $p(d_{i,j})$ for a given distance is lower than the preset threshold, the IIoTD avoids transmission. This is done with the hope that another IIoTD has a better observation of the event, thereby avoiding collisions in high-density scenarios, reducing re-transmissions, and conserving energy. This aligns transmission strategies with real-world signal dynamics, promoting more responsive and energy-efficient communication.

Herein, we aim to minimize the energy consumption in the network by optimizing $\delta = [\delta_1, \delta_2, \dots, \delta_N]^T$. Specifically, the optimization problem is stated as

$$\text{P1 : } \min_{\delta} W(\delta) \quad (2a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \mathbb{E}(P_e(\delta)) \leq E, \quad (2b)$$

where $P_e(\delta)$ is the error probability given the IIoTDs location and transmission threshold and a specific event realization, $\mathbb{E}(P_e)$ is its expected value with respect to the events'

epicenters, and E is a maximum error constraint. Meanwhile, $W(\delta)$ depicts the expected power consumption per IIoTD in the network, which obeys

$$W(\delta) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N \Pr(A_j). \quad (3)$$

This is a simplified energetic model, capturing only the proportion of time that the IIoTDs are in an active state. We disregard power consumption during idle periods due to its negligible impact on the overall analysis since the primary battery depletion factor in IIoTDs comes from radio interface usage [22]. We assume one transmission window (Tx) per TTI, so more than one IIoTD trying to access the medium at the TTI slot time (k^{th}) leads to a collision.

Collisions occur when multiple IIoTDs transmit their shared observations simultaneously, leading to data loss and increasing the expected error probability. However, note that failing to detect the presence of an event also increases the error probability. Given an IIoTD deployment, the event error probability P_e captures collision (P_{col}) and miss-detection (P_{miss}) probabilities after the occurrence of an event, *i.e.*,

$$P_e(\delta) = P_{\text{col}}(\delta) + P_{\text{miss}}(\delta), \quad (4)$$

since the coordinator does not receive information about this event in either case. The miss-detection probability is calculated as

$$P_{\text{miss}}(\delta) = \alpha \prod_{j=1}^N \Pr(p(d_{i,j}) < \delta_j) \quad (5)$$

due to the event not being detected by any sensor (miss-detection). Conversely, the probability of message notification losses due to collisions when several, more than one IIoTD, transmit at the same time is given by

$$P_{\text{col}}(\delta) = \alpha - P_{\text{miss}}(\delta) - P_{\text{suc}}(\delta), \quad (6)$$

where P_{suc} is the success probability. Therefore, we have that

$$P_e(\delta) = \alpha - P_{\text{suc}}(\delta). \quad (7)$$

Herein, P_{suc} refers to the union of the detection events from one and only one of the N sensors described as

$$P_{\text{suc}}(\delta) = \alpha \sum_{h=1}^N \left(\Pr(p(d_{i,h}) \geq \delta_h) \prod_{j \neq h} \Pr(p(d_{i,j}) < \delta_j) \right). \quad (8)$$

Then, the expected value in the network area is given by

$$\mathbb{E}(P_e(\delta)) = \alpha - \mathbb{E}(P_{\text{suc}}(\delta)) = \frac{1}{\mu(\xi)} \int_{\xi} P_e(\delta) \partial \mu, \quad (9)$$

where $\mu(\xi)$ is the Lebesgue measure of ξ , and $\int \partial \mu$ indicates a Lebesgue integration. In the specific case of a rectangular area with dimensions $L \times H$, (9) becomes

$$\mathbb{E}(P_e(\delta)) = \frac{1}{LH} \int_0^L \int_0^H P_e(\delta) \partial x \partial y. \quad (10)$$

IV. CONVEX OPTIMIZATION-BASED SOLUTION

Substituting $\alpha \Pr(e^{-\eta d_{i,j}} > \delta_j)$ into (3), the expected power consumption in the network obeys

$$W(\delta) = \frac{\alpha}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N \Pr(e^{-\eta d_{i,j}} > \delta_j). \quad (11)$$

This is monotonically increasing on $\Pr(e^{-\eta d_{i,j}} > \delta_j)$, which in turn is exponentially decreasing on δ_j . Then, the optimization problem can be reformulated as minimizing $\Pr(e^{-\eta d_{i,j}} > \delta_j)$ equivalent to $\Pr(d_{i,j} < -\ln(\delta_j)/\eta)$. Note that $d_{i,j} = \sqrt{(X - x_j)^2 + (Y - y_j)^2}$, where X and Y are uniformly randomly distributed in $[0, L]$ and $[0, H]$, respectively, and (x_j, y_j) is the known position of the IIoTD j .

Theorem 1: Let $Z = d_{i,j}^2 = (X - x_j)^2 + (Y - y_j)^2$, then

$$F_Z(z) \approx 1 - e^{-\frac{2z}{w}}, \text{ for } z \leq 200/\eta^2, \quad (12)$$

where $w = \max(x_j; L - x_j)^2 + \max(y_j; H - y_j)^2$. This approximation holds with high accuracy for practical IIoT deployments where sensing thresholds satisfy $\delta \in [10^{-4}, 1]$, corresponding to sensing radio up to 5 meters. Under these conditions, the approximation error remains below 3%, and the approximate expression converges to the exact CDF for small values of z .

Proof: See proof in Appendix A.

Therefore, $\Pr(d_{i,j} \leq -\ln(\delta_j)/\eta)$ can be reformulated as $\Pr(z_j \leq \ln^2(\delta_j)/\eta^2) = F_Z(\ln^2(\delta_j)/\eta^2)$, which is monotonically increasing, and P1 can be rewritten as

$$\text{P2: } \min_{\delta} \sum_{j=1}^N F_Z(\ln^2(\delta_j)/\eta^2) \quad (13a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \mathbb{E}(P_e(\delta)) \leq E. \quad (13b)$$

Herein, $\mathbb{E}(P_e(\delta))$ can be computed by substituting (8) into (9), wherein

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}(P_{\text{suc}}(\delta)) &= \alpha \sum_{h=1}^N \left(1 - e^{-\frac{2\ln^2(\delta_h)}{w_h}} \right) \prod_{j \neq h} e^{-\frac{2\ln^2(\delta_j)}{w_j}} \\ &= \alpha \sum_{h=1}^N \left(1 - e^{-\frac{2\ln^2(\delta_h)}{w_h}} \right) e^{-2 \sum_{j \neq h}^N \frac{\ln^2 \delta_j}{w_j}} \\ &= \alpha \sum_{h=1}^N e^{-2 \sum_{j \neq h}^N \frac{\ln^2 \delta_j}{w_j}} + \alpha N e^{-2 \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{\ln^2 \delta_j}{w_j}}. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Hence,

$$\mathbb{E}(P_e(\delta)) = \alpha - \alpha \sum_{h=1}^N e^{-2 \sum_{j \neq h}^N \frac{\ln^2 \delta_j}{w_j}} + \alpha N e^{-2 \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{\ln^2 \delta_j}{w_j}}. \quad (15)$$

However, solving this optimization problem is still non-trivial since the objective and constraint functions are not convex (see proof in Appendix B).

Convex optimization techniques have been promising in addressing various challenges in wireless communication

Algorithm 1 SCA

- 1: **Initialization:** Choose initial δ_0
 - 2: **for** $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, g - 1$ **do**
 - 3: **Solve** the surrogate problem using $\mathcal{T}(\cdot)$ around δ_k such that

$$\hat{\delta}_k = \arg \min_{\delta} W(\delta) \text{ s.t. } \mathbb{E}(P_e(\delta)) \leq E$$
 - 4: **Update** with learning rate ϑ_k : $\delta_{k+1} = \delta_k + \vartheta_k (\hat{\delta}_k - \delta_k)$
 - 5: **end for**
 - 6: **Return** δ_k
-

systems. Moreover, interior point methods (IPM), which are known to converge in/with polynomial time/complexity, are commonly utilized for solving convex problems [23]–[25]. In the following subsections, we will discuss the fundamental principles of convex approximation methods used in this paper and how they address P2. Such an optimization problem can be solved by iterative approximation methods like SCA [23], [26] or BCD [27], where an inner convex approximation in each iteration approximates the non-convex feasible set. By using the approximation methods, an approximate solution to the optimization problem in (13) can be attained using standard convex optimization tools such as CVX [26] or fmincon of MATLAB [28].

A. SUCCESSIVE CONVEX APPROXIMATION (SCA)

To solve P2 using SCA, we approximate the constraint function with its first-order Taylor series and iteratively optimize the objective function. Also, we use regularization to enforce convergence. Herein, we define $\mathcal{T}(\cdot)$ as the operator approximating an input function using its first-order Taylor series expansion. The first-order Taylor series approximation is used to estimate the constraint around δ_0 . This constraint is a vector of initial values of δ that gets updated in each SCA iteration by the resulting value obtained in the previous iteration. The error probability and its first derivative is evaluated in δ . Thus, it is given by

$$\mathcal{T}(\mathbb{E}(P_e(\delta))) = \mathbb{E}(P_e(\delta_0)) + (\delta - \delta_0)^T \nabla \mathbb{E}(P_e(\delta_0)), \quad (16)$$

where

$$\nabla_{\delta_j} \mathbb{E}(P_e(\delta)) = \frac{4\alpha \ln(\delta_j)}{w_j \delta_j} \left(\sum_{h=1}^{N-1} e^{-2 \sum_{i \neq h}^N \frac{\ln^2 \delta_i}{w_i}} - e^{-2 \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\ln^2 \delta_i}{w_i}} \right). \quad (17)$$

Algorithm 1 depicts the SCA algorithm for each iteration k . Note that the complexity when implementing SCA is $\mathcal{O}(gf(\delta))$, where g is the maximum number of iterations.

B. BLOCK COORDINATE DESCENDING METHOD (BCD)

In the conventional BCD framework, the formulated non-convex sparse recovery problem can be decomposed into small-scale sub-problems after exploiting the least absolute shrinkage and selection operator-based regularization [27]. Subsequently, the variables in each sub-problem can be optimized sequentially with variables from other sub-problems

Algorithm 2 BCD

- 1: **Initialization:** Choose initial δ_0
 - 2: **for** $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, g - 1$ **do**
 - 3: **for** $j = 1, 2, \dots, N$ **do**
 - 4: **Solve** P2 for variable $\hat{\delta}_j$ with $\delta_{h \neq j}$ fixed, i.e.,

$$\hat{\delta}_j = \arg \min_{\delta_j} W(\delta) \text{ s.t. } \mathbb{E}(P_e(\delta)) \leq E$$
 - 5: **end for**
 - 6: $\delta_{k+1} = \hat{\delta}_k$
 - 7: **end for**
 - 8: **Return** δ_k
-

kept fixed. Herein, we also approximate the constraint function with its first-order Taylor series, as in SCA, but in this case, the function has just one variable in each iteration, while the rest are fixed. The method runs N iterations in which the problem is solved for one variable at each step, fixing the rest of $(N - 1)$ variables, running N sequential problems with one variable in an inner loop, and repeating the method g times (maximum iteration). Algorithm 2 summarizes BCD algorithm and note that its complexity is $\mathcal{O}(gNf(\delta))$.

V. HEURISTIC & DATA-DRIVEN PROPOSED SOLUTIONS

Relying on previous optimization techniques can be computationally expensive and time-consuming, especially for large-scale IIoT systems. Herein, we aim to explore heuristic and data-driven approaches to efficiently solve the problem. Note that heuristic approaches may lead to near-optimal solutions relatively quickly. In contrast, data-driven solutions can learn from the available data and make predictions based on the learned patterns. Metaheuristic methods such as GA [29] and PSO [30] are valid tools, along with online methods like RL [31] and Lyapunov optimization [32], which also offer adaptability.

In the following, we present potential approaches to solve the problem. The first two solutions are heuristics, one based on the Voronoi diagram and the other on clustering and Bayes' theorem, specifically KNN. The third solution uses metaheuristic numerical methods and requires GA and PSO tools. The fourth and final approach is a RL-based solution. Notice that, unlike the metaheuristic methods, such heuristic learning can be performed online, as it does not require an oracle view of the network for re-training. Specifically, the sensors can independently implement and change strategies in case of re-training, using acknowledgments for correctly transmitted packets as their only feedback while knowing the position of the sensors (fixed) in its cluster and their threshold.

A. VORONOI-BASED APPROACH

Herein, we optimize δ using the Voronoi graph theory applied to the IIoT deployment. The principle of the Voronoi diagram has been maturely applied to computer graphics research, occupying an important role in computational ge-

FIGURE 3. Illustration of a Voronoi diagram for a grid IIoT deployment with 5 IIoTDs (represented as red dots). The black lines represent the Voronoi polygon corresponding to each IIoTD, while the blue lines represent the sensing area border. (left) Voronoi-(i), (center) Voronoi-(ii), and (right) Voronoi-(iii).

ometry [33]. A Voronoi diagram comprises a set of continuous polygons formed by vertical bisectors connecting two neighboring edges [34]. The bisector is the trajectory of all points at equal distances to neighboring IIoTD. A Voronoi diagram has three basic properties: (i) each Voronoi area is unique; (ii) the adjacent Voronoi area of each Voronoi area is the nearest adjacent area in the Euclidean plane; and (iii) each Voronoi area has at least three edges, and the edges are closed [34]. FIGURE 3 depicts a simple and easily interpretable Voronoi diagram of an IIoT deployment with 5 IIoTDs.

The Voronoi diagram's definition and unique properties can be harnessed to partition areas and employ the resulting polygons for each IIoTD as a metric for optimizing transmission thresholds. Specifically, we use the polygon metrics to calculate the optimal $\delta_j = e^{-\eta\Omega_j}$, where Ω_j (blue lines in FIGURE 3) represents the target coverage radio per IIoTD, and it is obtained by using three approaches as follows

- i) minimum distance from the IIoTD to its polygon;
- ii) mean distance from the IIoTD to its polygon;
- iii) maximum distance from the IIoTD to its polygon.

When employing a Voronoi-based approach, the worst-case complexity is $\mathcal{O}(2N \log N)$ [35].

B. BAYESIAN-BASED KNN

Recently, ML capabilities and utilization have tremendously increased in various fields. While cutting-edge ML models provide invaluable benefits, they often function as black boxes, which makes it difficult for humans to understand their decision-making processes. Indeed, complex models such as deep neural networks have multiple parameters and intricate structures to the point of being considered black boxes with low understandability.

The demand for transparency has prompted the emergence of Explainable AI (XAI). XAI is a field dedicated to developing AI methods that serve two primary objectives: i) to generate more comprehensible models while ensuring their

FIGURE 4. The trade-off between model interpretability and performance.

learning efficiency remains high and ii) to enable humans to trust, understand, and effectively manage these AI systems. Note, for instance, that ML models such as linear/logistic regression, decision trees, KNN, rule-based learners, general additive models, and Bayesian models are more easily understood and manipulated by humans. These models are transparent by design and have a greater explaining capacity than complex models like deep neural networks, as depicted in FIGURE 4, inspired in [36].

Herein, we adopt KNN [37], [38] and Bayesian Models [39], widely used XAI approaches in the IIoT context because of their trade-off accuracy/interpretability and simplicity. Specifically, we propose a heuristic approach wherein we form clusters based on each IIoTD's spatial placement using KNN, thus each data point is connected to its K-nearest neighbors, creating a graph structure. Note that the considered IIoT network is stationary, *i.e.*, IIoTDs' positions are fixed and known, thus the computational cost associated with implementing KNN is $\mathcal{O}(N(N-1)/2)$ in the worst-case scenario (brute force). This complexity arises due to the need to calculate distances to the N IIoTD for each query point. The search involves scanning the entire dataset to identify the KNN. However, as previously mentioned, the

FIGURE 5. Illustration of an IIoT deployment clustering with 30 IIoTDs and 4 clusters. The dot lines represent the cluster edges and the black dots represent IIoTDs acting as cluster heads.

computation time can differ based on the utilized algorithm, occasionally reducing to $\mathcal{O}(\min\{M(N - M), (N - M)^2\})$, where M is the number of clusters [35]. Note that we only form clusters once for a given IIoTD deployment, thus it can be implemented offline.

After establishing the clusters, as depicted in FIGURE 5 (see also FIGURE 1) as an example, we employ a greedy conditional probability rule, the generalized Bayes' rule. We start from the edges that statistically require a larger sensing area, *i.e.*, a lower threshold, to cover the entire area effectively and prevent miss-detection. Each IIoTD constitutes the center of a cluster according to the spatial correlation to its nearest neighbors, forming a graph structure. Initially, the IIoTDs' activation probability is set randomly. Then, we begin by updating the transmission threshold for each IIoTD by taking into account its spatial correlation with its nearest neighbors. We calculate δ_j based on the transmission thresholds of the neighbors and its transmission threshold, taking into account the spatial correlation as well. Then,

$$\Pr(p(d_{i,j}) \geq \delta_j) = \sum_{\forall h} \Pr(A_j|A_h) \Pr(p(d_{i,h}) \geq \delta_h), \quad (18)$$

where $\Pr(A_j|A_h)$ is the conditional probability for the IIoTD j^{th} IIoTD being active given that the h^{th} IIoTD is active.

Theorem 2: Let $R = \min(x_h, y_h, H - x_h, L - y_h)$ and $r = \max(R, d_h)$, then

$$\Pr(A_j|A_h) = 1 - \frac{\cos^{-1}\left(\frac{d_{i,h}^2 + r_{j,h}^2 - \ln^2(\delta_j)/\eta^2}{2d_{i,j}r_{j,h}}\right)}{2\pi - 8\cos^{-1}(R/r)}, \quad (19)$$

where $r_{j,h}$ is the distance between the IIoTDs j and h , and φ represents the angle at the event epicenter determined by the IIoTDs j and h positions.

Proof: See proof in Appendix C.

Finally, the complexity when implementing the Bayesian-based KNN algorithm is bounded by $\mathcal{O}(gN + \min\{M(N - M), (N - M)^2\})$, where g is the maximum number of iterations to converge. Note that the required iterations vary depending on the initial value for δ .

C. GENETIC ALGORITHM (GA)

We employ a GA for its capacity to explore extensive solution spaces and tackle nonlinear, non-convex problems

efficiently. GAs are well-suited for parallelization and scalability [40] and adapt to dynamic and changing environments. Unlike black-box approaches, GAs provide flexibility and adaptability while maintaining transparency [41], [42]. These meta-heuristic algorithms inspired by biological evolution are straightforward to construct and demand relatively modest storage.

GAs systematically explore the state space and iteratively apply mutation, crossover, and selection operations [29]. Specifically, an initial population of size Θ with potential solutions is generated first. Different δ initialization are generated with random threshold values. Note that increasing the population size increases the probability of finding a near-optimal solution, but the execution complexity also increases. The best-fit potential solutions are probabilistically selected from the current population based on the objective and constraint functions of (13). Then, the threshold parameters for each IIoTD undergo modifications, including recombination and potential random mutations, to generate a new generation [29]. Crossover combines activation probabilities of IIoTDs from different parent solutions, while mutation introduces random changes in these probabilities to promote exploration. The algorithm works by repeatedly going through a process of evolution, where the population changes over time and individuals are adjusted based on their fitness until an optimal or near-optimal solution is found. This process continues until either the optimization objective is met or the maximum number of iterations is reached (as defined by the parameter g).

Using this meta-heuristic algorithm, we approximate a near-optimal configuration with a complexity of $\mathcal{O}(g\beta)$, where g is the maximum number of iterations, and β represents the cardinality of the candidate population vector, which depends on the parameter values N and Θ as follows, $\beta = N\Theta$. Parameter fitness is assessed in each generation using the objective and constraint functions in (13).

D. PARTICLE SWARM OPTIMIZATION (PSO)

PSO is exceptional in dynamic and nonlinear spaces with a high complexity degree [30] and thus it is a compelling choice for addressing P2. PSO operates on the principles of swarm intelligence, mirroring the collaborative behavior of particles in nature. This is appealing in IIoT systems, where numerous IIoTDs must work together efficiently [30], [43].

Like in GA, a population Θ of threshold sets is randomly initialized within the threshold space $(0, 1]$, where each threshold set represents a potential solution. Then, we evaluate the potential solutions using (13) and based on the optimization goal. In each iteration, the threshold sets adjust their activation probabilities based on knowledge of better individual and global solutions discovered by themselves and the swarm. Specifically, we determine δ_j for each IIoTD by using a fixed value for the other IIoTDs' thresholds and selecting the best potential solutions in the population. At each iteration, we assess the fitness of each

particle's solution using (13), then update the individual δ_j and global best δ based on any improvements in fitness. This allows us to refine and improve the overall solution. PSO continues iterations until an optimal or near-optimal solution that satisfies the optimization objective is found, or the number of iterations parameter (g) reaches the preset maximum number. The best global solution found represents optimized activation probabilities. Herein, we approximate a near-optimal configuration using PSO with a complexity of $\mathcal{O}(gN\Theta)$. Note that the population of potential solutions can be initialized based on the spatial correlation relation from heuristics like Voronoi, which may decrease the complexity to reach a near-optimal solution.

E. REINFORCEMENT LEARNING (RL)

Model-free RL tackles decision-making challenges and learn optimal solutions in dynamic environments [44]. Herein, we reframe the optimization problem by introducing spatially-based transmission thresholds and approach it as RL challenge. The IIoT system is conceptualized as the environment, while the IIoTDs function as learning agents in this setup. A coordinator retains decision-making authority to prevent computational overload at the IIoTDs, representing them virtually. The central controller stationed at the coordinator provides notifications for miss-detection and collisions. The fundamental components of RL are described as follows.

Let \mathcal{S} denote the system state space. The current system state $s \in \mathcal{S}$ includes the state of each IIoTD (active or inactive) and their received sensing power from the event, depicted by the sensing function $p(d_{i,j})$. Consequently, it also includes information corresponding to collisions and miss-detections. In addition, the known position of the IIoTDs and their current thresholds are also known. The current state of each IIoTD is defined as

$$s = \{\{\delta_j\}_{\forall j \in \mathcal{J}}, \{p(d_{i,j})\}_{\forall j \in \mathcal{J}}, \{(x_j, y_j)\}_{\forall j \in \mathcal{J}}\}. \quad (20)$$

With an observed state 's' given, the coordinator varies δ for each IIoTD according to the reward/penalty function. The action space is then delimited by threshold limits as $\delta_j \in (0; 1]; \forall j \in \mathcal{J}$. The reward must capture the effectiveness of the threshold policy when the agent takes an action in the current state. In each learning step, the system's performance must align with the reward function [44], enhancing energy efficiency while avoiding errors. This reward function represents our optimization goal, which is to maximize the system's overall energy efficiency. Therefore, the reward function at a TTI τ is expressed as

$$r_\tau = \sum_{j,h \in \mathcal{J}} \Pr(A_j|A_h) \Pr(p(d_{i,j}) \geq \delta_h) - \mu_1 p(d_{i,j}) \rho_j - \mu_2 p(d_{i,j}) \sigma, \quad (21)$$

where the coefficients μ_1 and μ_2 are the positive constants used to balance the utility and cost. Additionally, $\Pr(A_j|A_h)$ accounts for the conditional activation probability between IIoTD in position (x_j, y_j) given an active IIoTD in (x_h, y_h) . On the other hand, the second and last terms are penalized

to account for situations that provoke error. Specifically, ρ_j accounts for the collision effect factor given by

$$\rho_j = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if collision occurs and } \Pr(p(d_{i,j}) \geq \delta_j), \\ -1, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

Moreover, σ is the miss-detection factor given by

$$\sigma = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if no IIoTD is active,} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

Herein, we assume that the coordinator detects event miss-detection during training. Note that ρ_j and σ impose the error probability satisfaction level. If no collision or miss-detection occurs, then $\rho_j = 0$ or $\sigma = 0$, indicating no penalization to the reward function due to any error. The goal is to find the policy π^* at each state τ (mapping states in \mathcal{S} to the probability of choosing an action $\pi_j^*(s) \in [-\delta_j^*, 1 - \delta_j^*]$, with $s_\tau + \pi^* \rightarrow s_{\tau+1}$) [31] that maximizes the long-term expected discounted reward. The cumulative discounted reward is given by

$$U_\tau = \sum_{k=0}^{\tau} \zeta^k r_{k+1}, \quad (24)$$

where $\zeta \in (0, 1]$ is the discount factor that grows exponentially with each state τ and $r_{\tau+1}$ is the reward at the next state.

Moreover, the state-action function of the agent with a state-action pair (s, a) under a policy π is given by

$$Q_\tau^\pi(s_\tau, a_\tau) = \mathbb{E}_\pi[U_\tau | s = s_\tau, a = a_\tau], \quad (25)$$

where a conventional Q -learning algorithm can be adapted to learn the optimal policy by updating the Q -table using Bellman's equation to reach the optimal action-value function [45]. Furthermore, the Q -value is updated as follows

$$Q_{\tau+1}^\pi(s_\tau, a_\tau) = (1 - \omega_\tau) Q_\tau^\pi(s_\tau, a_\tau) + \dots + \omega_\tau (r_\tau + \zeta_\tau \max_{a_\tau} Q_\tau^{\pi^*}(s_{\tau+1}, a_{\tau+1})), \quad (26)$$

where $\omega_\tau \in (0, 1]$ is the learning rate. In this paper, we adopt Q -learning because it provides high interpretability and computational simplicity through its tabular structure and Bellman updates. This approach avoids the complex neural network training required by other RL methods, such as deep RL (DRL) or policy gradient techniques. This is particularly attractive in IIoT environments [46], [47], where IIoTDs often have low memory and low power. Additionally, Q -learning enables offline policy training, allowing deployment without frequent retraining or synchronization, unlike DRL-based methods. All in all, Q -learning provides an efficient trade-off between interpretability, computational efficiency, and adaptability for our IIoT system scenario.

Q -Learning generally constructs a lookup Q -table $Q(s, a)$, and the agent selects actions based on an ϵ -greedy policy for each learning step [48]. In the ϵ -greedy policy, the agent chooses the action with the maximum Q -table value with probability $(1 - \epsilon)$, whereas a random action is picked with probability ϵ to support exploration and avoid getting stuck

at non-optimal policies [44]. Once the optimal Q -function $Q^*(s, a)$ is achieved, the optimal policy is determined by

$$\pi^*(s, a) = \arg \max_{a_\tau} Q^*(s, a). \quad (27)$$

Q -learning does not require a predefined model of the environment. Instead, it learns by continuously adjusting its decisions in real time based on the experienced rewards. Furthermore, the ϵ -greedy policy considers the exploration of new actions (to discover better strategies) and the exploitation of prior knowledge (to ensure stability) [47]. This allows new IIoTDs to join the network without compromising previously learned knowledge. Therefore, Q -learning can quickly respond to unpredictable fluctuations and effectively adapt to multi-device environments where conditions change rapidly.

The computational complexity of this approach can vary depending on the initial values and the specific implementation of the algorithm. While the worst-case algorithmic complexity is $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$, this bound is rather loose in practice. Each learning step typically involves only the subset of IIoTDs located within 5 meters of the event epicenter, consistent with the sensing range limitations assumed in Theorem 1. Consequently, only a limited number of IIoTDs are affected by any given event and participate in the reward computation. This localized processing significantly reduces the computational load, making the method both scalable and efficient. Overall, it achieves a practical balance between complexity and adaptability for large-scale IIoT deployments.

VI. COMPLEXITY ANALYSIS

Herein, we summarize and discuss the complexity of the proposed optimization algorithms. We compare our proposals with a conventional implementation where each IIoTD has the same threshold (sensitivity) configured [17], *i.e.*, $\delta_j = \delta, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}$. Notice that the problem in (13) is easily solved for an equal activation threshold since the sum and multiplication of probabilities in the objective and constraint function become an arithmetic and geometric mean with only one variable (see Appendix D).

The complexity for equal- δ , SCA, and BCD depends on the complexity of performing IPM to solve $f(\delta)$ [49], which depends on the inequality constraints and the complexity of a typically polynomial method. In this case, there is just one inequality constraint and the worst-case complexity to solve the problem using IPM is $\mathcal{O}(N^3)$ and typically converges for $g = \sqrt{N}$ iterations. Note that this value varies depending on the suitability of the initial values. Here, for equal- δ and BCD, the problem is evaluated in a summation of N terms with one variable, thus the complexity is $\mathcal{O}(N^3)$ for equal δ while for BCD is $\mathcal{O}(N^{9/2})$ since the problem is solved N times and converges in \sqrt{N} . Meanwhile, the complexity for SCA is $\mathcal{O}(N^{7/2})$ since there is a summation of N terms with a vector δ of N variables. Without losing generality, we assume that the complexity of evaluating a variable is $\mathcal{O}(1)$.

TABLE 2. Complexity Analysis

Algorithm	Complexity
Equal δ	$\mathcal{O}(N^3)$
SCA	$\mathcal{O}(N^3\sqrt{N})$
BCD	$\mathcal{O}(N^4\sqrt{N})$
Voronoi	$\mathcal{O}(N \log N)$
Bayesian-based KNN	$\mathcal{O}(gN + (N - M)(\min\{M, N - M\}))$
GA	$\mathcal{O}(gN\Theta)$
PSO	$\mathcal{O}(gN\Theta)$
RL	$\mathcal{O}(N^2)$

Note that good choices of g and Θ may increase with N .

Table 2 summarizes the complexity of the analyzed methods in terms of the Big \mathcal{O} notation. The equal- δ and Voronoi approaches exhibit iteration-independent convergence, whereas the rest involve iterative procedures whose complexity depends on factors such as the number of variables, convergence criteria, and initialization strategies. Note that the computational complexity of these methods scales polynomially with the number of IIoTDs N . BCD is the most complex method, while Voronoi and KNN are comparatively the least. Although RL is the most energy-efficient method, it is the only one that requires online implementation or a quite wide dataset. Note that if RL is implemented with an initial δ based on the output from previous algorithms (*e.g.*, SCA or Voronoi), rather than random initialization, its complexity decreases up to $\mathcal{O}(N \log N)$. This enables flexible RL deployment through offline training with historical data and periodic retraining in dynamic environments.

VII. PRACTICAL CONSIDERATIONS

We assume that the IIoTDs are static or quasi-static, and that both their positions and the event statistics (*i.e.*, α) are perfectly known by the BS. Indeed, the device locations may be known from deployment records, reported by the IIoTDs, or estimated in advanced by the BS through localization techniques. Event statistics, in turn, can be estimated or learned over time. In practice, α can be derived from historical data. Note that our methods do not require complete distributional models, but an estimate of the mean event occurrence rate is sufficient. We also assume equal transmission power across all IIoTDs to simplify the analysis and isolate the effects of transmission strategies. While IIoT deployments often include heterogeneous IIoTDs, many of them operate under standardized or pre-configured power settings to ensure dependability and regulatory compliance [50]. This assumption is also valid in homogeneous deployments, such as smart buildings or agricultural monitoring, where all IIoTDs are typically of the same brand and model, sharing similar power configurations.

TABLE 3. Practical Considerations for the Optimization Methods

Method	Relying on α	Advantages	Challenges	Best use case	Explainability
Equal δ	✓	Simple and highly scalable	Spatial deployment information is not exploited	Uniform/regular IIoT deployments	Interpretable
SCA	✓	Ensures local optimal solutions	Sensitive to initialization; limited scalability; computationally intensive	Non-massive IIoT optimization with known event statistics	Interpretable
BCD	✓	Ensures local optimal solutions; breaks the problems into blocks;	Sensitive to initialization; could be time expensive	Non-massive IIoT optimization with known event statistics	Interpretable
Voronoi		Highly scalable for spatial coordination	Limited performance in non-uniform IIoT deployments	Uniform/regular IIoT deployments	Interpretable
Bayesian-based KNN		Lightweight and interpretable; effective for localized problems	Performance degrades in high-density scenarios without efficient pre-selection or dimensionality reduction	Dynamically and localized adjustments with positional data	Explainable
GA	✓	Robust global exploration of large, complex solution spaces	Poor scalability; high computational cost and slow convergence for massive IIoT	Static IIoT scenario	Black-Box
PSO	✓	Scalable with parallelization; balances exploration and exploitation	Scalability limited without parallelization; prone to premature convergence	Static IIoT systems	Black-Box
RL	✓	Dynamically adaptive to failures and changes; scalable with pre-trained models	High computation cost for real-time massive systems without pre-trained models	Real-time adjustments in dynamic or failure-prone networks	Black-Box

Our proposed system adopts a compatible IIoTD–edge–cloud architecture, in which the BS or an edge computing node centrally executes the intelligent optimization and activation management strategy. This approach aligns with current 3GPP standardization efforts for dependable IIoT network management [51]. Edge nodes perform threshold tuning and transmission strategy optimization, using lightweight protocols to configure IIoTDs. Algorithms operate offline and update dynamically at the edge, ensuring adaptive and scalable performance without continuous communication. Centralized processing (at the BS or edge server) manages computationally intensive tasks, such as heavy optimization or transmission threshold estimation. Only finalized configuration parameters (*e.g.*, updated transmission thresholds) are deployed to IIoTDs, preserving their low-power operation. To ensure the system operates with parameters that adapt to changing scenario conditions, a reconfiguration mechanism is only triggered by significant changes in traffic patterns or IIoTD locations, which drastically reduces control signaling overhead. Herein, we neglect device battery limitations and failure issues, enabling a focused evaluation of device activation management strategies.

It is important to note that methods such as SCA, BCD, GA, and PSO are particularly suitable for scenarios that demand accurate modeling of event-driven traffic to optimize power consumption, as their operation depends on prior knowledge of event occurrence statistics. However, methods like RL and Bayesian-based KNN are better suitable for

dynamically adjusting δ in response to network changes, such as device failures or irregular and non-uniform event occurrence. These methods include RL, Voronoi diagrams, and Bayesian-based KNN, which exploit spatial relationships and feedback mechanisms rather than explicit event probabilities. It is also important to note that, while exact IIoTD positioning is assumed in the system model, practical deployments may rely on estimated positions subject to localization error. Accordingly, 3GPP Release 17 specifies a maximum horizontal localization error of 20 cm for IIoT scenarios [52], while Release 18 introduces advanced techniques capable of achieving sub-10 cm, or centimeter-level, accuracy [53]. When estimation errors stay within this range, the proposed methods typically experience negligible performance degradation. However, as the error increases, performance can degrade substantially due to the distance-dependent nature of the sensing function. In such cases, robust optimization methods, using worst-case or probabilistic formulations, should be considered to ensure resilient operation. Notably, the RL-based method is expected to be more tolerant to such uncertainty, as it relies on feedback rather than precise spatial information, and can operate effectively without exact position estimates.

In massive IIoT scenarios where scalability is crucial, methods like Voronoi and RL offer advantages due to their ability to optimize subsets of IIoTDs independently. In contrast, GA, PSO, BCD, and SCA face challenges because of their high computational costs and slower convergence.

Nevertheless, Bayesian-based KNN can be applied in these large-scale scenarios. Hybrid approaches that combine scalable methods such as Voronoi for initial exploration with dynamic policies like RL or KNN can significantly improve overall performance. Thus, in real-time scenarios, combining methods based on their respective strengths and weaknesses is the most effective strategy. For initial optimization, techniques like Voronoi, GA, or PSO can be utilized, while convex methods such as SCA and BCD can offer refinement and more precise optimization. Subsequently, employing mechanisms like RL and KNN for real-time adjustments and localized decision-making ensures scalability, efficiency, and robustness when addressing dynamic and spatial challenges within IIoT systems. The strengths and weaknesses of each method are summarized in Table 3.

VIII. RESULTS

Consider a $50 \times 50 \text{ m}^2$ area with $N \in [25, 1000]$ IIoTDs, corresponding to densities ranging from 0.01 to 0.4 IIoTDs/m^2 . This range spans from sparse to ultra-dense IIoT scenarios. Notably, densities above 0.3 IIoTDs/m^2 are commonly associated with critical IIoT use cases, such as high-resolution monitoring and real-time control [54], [55]. We choose $N \geq 25$ since for smaller numbers the optimization problem often becomes unfeasible as there are not enough IIoTDs to cover the area. Indeed, miss-detection events are very common for $N < 25$. Additionally, we consider $\alpha = 0.1$, $\eta = 1$ [16], and $g = \sqrt{N}$. We set $E = 0.01$ to represent a 99% event detection reliability target, which corresponds to typical dependability requirements found in low-power IIoT scenarios, striking a balance between energy efficiency and reliability [56]. We performed 250 Monte Carlo iterations corresponding to different deployments to ensure statistical reliability of the results. This sample size enables robust performance metrics and supports significance testing using p-values, which allows us to differentiate true performance differences from stochastic variation [57]. Moreover, the initial value δ_0 for the optimization methods SCA, BCD, KNN, and RL is set according to (46), see Appendix D.

A. PERFORMANCE METRICS

Herein, we discuss power consumption, error probability, and feasibility as metrics to evaluate the performance of the discussed frameworks.

We employ a simplified model that concentrates exclusively on the power consumption of the radio frequency interface, as this is the primary factor contributing to battery depletion in IIoTDs [22]. This simplification allows us to neglect the power consumed during idle/sensing states, which is significantly lower compared to that used during active transmission. The adopted metric corresponds to the normalized expected power consumption given in (11), representing the average proportion of time an IIoTD spends in active transmission. As such, the value of W is a unitary quantity.

In addition, the error probability is given in (16) while we evaluate the feasibility of each method for conveying the optimization problem and fulfilling the constraints related to error probability. The feasibility is expressed as $\Pr(\mathbb{E}(P_e(\delta)) \leq E)$. We assess the performance of the proposed methods based on two criteria: sensing coverage and overlapping area. The sensing coverage refers to the portion of the network that lies within the sensing radius of at least one IIoTD, while the overlapping area is defined as the portion of the network that falls within the sensing radius of more than one IIoTD. Finally, execution time refers to the time each method requires to reach its minimum power consumption value during the optimization process.

B. BENCHMARK AND VORONOI APPROACHES

We adopt the equal- δ approach as a benchmark. Initially, we assess the power consumption linked to employing the equal- δ approach and compare it with the four Voronoi-based solutions. It's noteworthy that the optimization problem might not always be solvable with the equal- δ approach and the latter three Voronoi-based alternatives, due to non-compliance with the error constraints.

In FIGURE 6, we show the mean energy consumption per IIoTD in the network when using the two previous solutions. Note that the Voronoi-(i) algorithm has the best performance, while the scenario with equal- δ and Voronoi-(iii) has the worst performance related to energy consumption. Herein, note that equal- δ slightly outperforms Voronoi-(iii) for more than 33 IIoTDs. Indeed, the sensing area in the latter approach is determined by the biggest distance to the Voronoi polygon, hence, the overlapping probability in sensing areas for neighbor IIoTD is high and the energy efficiency low. However, Voronoi-(i) is the only algorithm capable of finding a solution to the optimization problem in each scenario. The other approaches can find solutions in just some cases, as depicted in FIGURE 7. In this case, both approaches with the worst performance can find a solution between 49% (equal- δ) to 55% (Voronoi-(iii)) of the time, while the feasibility is about 72%-74% for Voronoi-(ii).

Based on the above discussions, only the Voronoi-(i) approach is adopted for comparison purposes in the following. It is worth noting that the equal- δ solution, although not always feasible according to the constraint, will still be included in the comparisons for benchmarking purposes.

C. PERFORMANCE COMPARISON

Herein, we present performance results for the proposed energy-efficient solutions. Notably, these solutions are feasible across all 250 modeled scenarios, unlike the benchmark and Voronoi's approaches analyzed in Section VIII-B. Specifically, FIGURE 8 shows the power consumption per device as a function of the device density and using the approximation methods. Herein, BCD and RL have the worst and best performance, respectively. The RL approach significantly reduces power consumption, achieving reductions

FIGURE 6. Normalized power consumption as a function of the number of IIoTDs for the benchmark and the Voronoi approaches.

FIGURE 7. Feasibility rate to find a configuration with $P_e \leq 0.1$ as a function of the number of IIoTDs for the benchmark and Voronoi's approaches.

of up to 95% in low-density scenarios and 63% in high-density scenarios relative to the benchmark. These results are further validated by p -values obtained from the Monte Carlo simulations, all of which meet the significance threshold of $p \leq 0.04$. Moreover, in high-density deployments, the RL-based method proves particularly effective at capturing underlying correlations in IIoTD activations and spatial event influence. This is achieved by focusing on relevant IIoTDs per event rather than involving the entire network. In contrast, the other methods rely on global optimizations involving all IIoTDs, which increases complexity as IIoTD density grows. As a result, these approaches struggle to sustain performance, while the RL-based method delivers a more substantial reduction in power consumption and maintains scalability. Interestingly, SCA and KNN offer the next best performance after RL; however, beyond 250 IIoTDs, their power consumption tend to remain constant, while RL continues to improve. Meanwhile, GA and PSO

perform similarly and outperform the equal- δ approach only for a density below 250 IIoTDs. On the other hand, BCD outperforms the equal threshold scheme for a density below 150 IIoTDs. However, it consumes more power when the density increases above 150. Notice that for the equal- δ scenario, the error probability constraints can not be met for around half of the scenarios modeled. In general, the power consumption decreases with the number of IIoTDs, since the sensing area is smaller for each IIoTD, which reduces their activation probability across most approaches.

FIGURE 8. Normalized power consumption as a function of the number of IIoTDs for the proposed solutions.

FIGURE 9 illustrates the percentage of the area wherein at least two IIoTDs are likely to collide due to concurrent event sensing/detection. When the network density remains below 300 IIoTDs, such an overlapping area is kept under 10–11% across all methods. However, as the number of IIoTDs increases to 1000, the proposed methods based on GA, PSO, and Voronoi diagrams fail to maintain the overlapping area at low levels, whereas the RL and convex-based methods perform the best. Moreover, we illustrate the coverage area, i.e., the % of the area covered by at least one IIoTD, supported by each method in FIGURE 10 since this, together with the overlapping area, finally determine the error probability. In low-density scenarios, the RL and convex-based methods perform the best, while the equal threshold and Voronoi-based approaches perform the worst, covering less than 94% of the network area. Conversely, in high-density scenarios, all proposed methods, except for the GA-based approach, can provide over 98% coverage, effectively minimizing the risk of missed detections. It is also noteworthy that as the IIoTD density increases, the proposed methods slightly reduce the individual coverage areas to minimize overlap and better satisfy the optimization constraints.

The proposed optimization methods exhibit different theoretical computational complexities, as indicated in Sec-

FIGURE 9. Overlapping sensing area as a function of the number of IIoTDs for the proposed solutions.

FIGURE 11. Comparison of the execution time in seconds for the proposed optimization methods as a function of the number of IIoTDs.

FIGURE 10. Coverage area as a function of the number of IIoTDs for the proposed solutions.

tion VI. To validate these analytical findings, we present an empirical evaluation of the execution time required by each method to reach convergence. FIGURE 11 shows a comparative analysis of the execution time of the proposed optimization methods as a function of the number of IIoTDs (N). The figure illustrates the time required by each method to achieve the minimum power consumption during the training phase. Methods with lower computational complexity, such as KNN, Voronoi-based clustering, and RL, converge significantly faster than the rest. Optimization techniques like SCA and BCD incur substantially higher computational costs as N increases. The equal- δ benchmark relies on the closed-form solution derived in Appendix D, which is more computationally efficient than traditional IPM. All the experiments were conducted on a Lenovo ThinkPad laptop equipped with an Intel® Core™ i7-12700H processor, 16 GB of RAM, and running MATLAB® R2023a on Windows 11.

In addition, FIGURE 12 displays P_e , which combines the collision (cyan) and miss-detection (green) probabilities for the proposed methods and the equal- δ benchmark. While all proposed methods maintain P_e below 0.01 in low to moderate-density scenarios, only the SCA, BCD, RL-based, and Bayesian-based KNN approaches consistently satisfy the constraint across all densities. In contrast, the equal- δ benchmark fails to ensure compliance with the constraint. Across all configurations, P_{miss} remains almost constant, with values consistently below 0.001, indicating that variations in P_e are primarily due to collision probability. As IIoTD density increases, P_e rises due to the higher probability of concurrent transmissions triggered by the same event, leading to elevated collision rates. Among the proposed methods, the RL-based approach achieves the lowest P_e , whereas BCD, GA, and PSO exhibit the highest values. In low-density scenarios, SCA, KNN, and RL yield additional reductions in error probability of up to 45.7%, 28.2%, and 0.7% relative to the equal- δ baseline, respectively. However, in high-density conditions, only the RL-based and Bayesian-based KNN approaches sustain performance improvements, achieving reductions in error probability of up to 17% and 42%, respectively.

Noteworthy, employing BCD requires a computational cost N times higher than that of SCA. This is even though each iteration in SCA is slightly more complex to execute. Furthermore, RL requires access to additional historical data characterizing the IIoTD traffic and activation behavior to facilitate learning, which makes the training a little more complex but gives additional online support for a dynamic scenario. Note that the value of η does not affect the power consumption of our proposed methods. This is because the transmission threshold is adjusted based on the value of η , but the sensor area itself remains constant.

FIGURE 12. Error probability (P_e) for the proposed solutions as the sum of the collision (cyan) and miss-detection (green) probabilities for (left) 50, (center) 150, and (right) 250 IIoTds. The percentages indicate the error probability of the methods compared to the equal- δ approach, while the red dotted line represents the error constraint E .

IX. CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposed adaptive transmission strategies for IIoTds exploiting their sensing/activation spatial correlations. The idea is for the IIoTds to use transmission thresholds properly configured to reduce power consumption without compromising event detection reliability. To this end, we formulated an optimization problem for threshold configuration and presented multiple solution strategies, including convex methods such as SCA and BCD; and heuristic methods like Voronoi diagrams, explainable ML, and algorithms based on natural selection and social behavior. Additionally, we reformulated the problem as a form of RL, employing Q -learning. We showed that the complexity of the proposed methods is polynomial, with BCD as the most complex, and Voronoi and KNN as the least complex. Notably, the RL-based approach is especially effective for real-time adaptability, achieving superior performance across varying network densities. Meanwhile, methods like Voronoi-based clustering and KNN strike a balance between interpretability and computational efficiency. Our proposals achieved a power consumption reduction ranging from 63% to 95% compared to the equal- δ benchmark in a variety of tested scenarios, spanning from high to low density. As the IIoTds density increases, the transmission thresholds progressively converge toward 1, indicating that only IIoTds with highly relevant observations are permitted to transmit, while the majority remain inactive. This behavior reflects the models capacity to reduce redundant transmissions in ultra-dense deployments while preserving detection reliability. Overall, the findings highlight the necessity of data-driven and spatially aware decision-making for optimizing event detection in IIoT environments.

In future work, we plan to investigate adaptive methods for dynamically optimizing transmission thresholds based on non-stationary network conditions and IIoTds-specific attributes. This could involve developing algorithms that adjust thresholds in real-time to maximize energy efficiency while ensuring a target performance level. The results presented in this paper also encourage further research on cooperative and distributed sensing strategies, such as group-based schemes or joint clustering and thresholding approaches,

where IIoTds coordinate their operation to balance energy consumption and sensing accuracy. Such coordination mechanisms may also serve as a built-in redundancy strategy, enhancing dependability in dense and critical deployment scenarios. Furthermore, future efforts should also consider threshold optimization under uncertain or imperfect IIoTds position information, relaxing the current assumption of perfect location knowledge and enabling more robust performance in practical deployments.

APPENDIX A. CDF of $d_{i,j}$

The variable $(X - x_j)$ has a uniform probability distribution function (PDF) $\frac{1}{L} \in [-x_j, L - x_j]$ and the PDF of $\hat{X} \triangleq (X - x_j)^2$ is given by [58]

$$f_{\hat{X}}(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{u\sqrt{\hat{X}}}, & 0 \leq \hat{X} \leq \min(x_j; L - x_j)^2, \\ \frac{1}{2u\sqrt{\hat{X}}}, & \min(x_j; L - x_j)^2 < \hat{X} \leq u, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

where $u = \max(x_j; L - x_j)^2$. Likewise, let us denote $\hat{Y} \triangleq (Y - y_j)^2$, and then

$$f_{\hat{Y}}(y) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{v\sqrt{\hat{Y}}}, & 0 \leq \hat{Y} \leq \min(y_j; H - y_j)^2, \\ \frac{1}{2v\sqrt{\hat{Y}}}, & \min(y_j; H - y_j)^2 < \hat{Y} \leq v, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (29)$$

where $v = \max(y_j; H - y_j)^2$. Next, given $Z = d_{i,j}^2 = \hat{X} + \hat{Y}$ and knowing that \hat{X} and \hat{Y} are independent variables, the CDF of the variable Z , denoted as $F_Z(z)$, is calculated as $\Pr(\hat{X} + \hat{Y} \leq z)$

$$F_Z(z) = \int_0^u \int_0^{z-x} f_{\hat{X}}(x) f_{\hat{Y}}(y) \partial y \partial x = \frac{2}{uv} \int_0^u \frac{\sqrt{z-x}}{\sqrt{x}} \partial x. \quad (30)$$

FIGURE 13. Approximation to (33) for different u, v and η values, (top) $u, v = 25$ and (bottom) $u, v = 50$.

Then, using $q = \sqrt{x}$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} F_Z(z) &= \frac{2}{uv} \int_0^{\sqrt{x}} 2\sqrt{z - q^2} \partial q \\ &= \frac{4}{uv} \int_0^{\sqrt{x}} \sqrt{z \left(1 - \frac{q^2}{z}\right)} \partial q \\ &= \frac{4\sqrt{z}}{uv} \int_0^{\sqrt{x}} \sqrt{1 - \frac{q^2}{z}} \partial q. \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

Next, applying trigonometric substitution we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} F_Z(z) &= \frac{4\sqrt{z}}{uv} \int_0^{\arcsin(\sqrt{1/z}\sqrt{x})} \sqrt{z} \cos^2(v) \partial v \\ &= \frac{4z}{uv} \int_0^{\arcsin(\sqrt{1/z}\sqrt{x})} \cos^2(v) \partial v \\ &= \frac{4z}{uv} \int_0^{\arcsin(\sqrt{1/z}\sqrt{x})} \frac{1 + \cos(2v)}{2} \partial v, \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

where the last step comes from using the trigonometric identities $\cos 2\phi + 2\sin^2 \phi = 1$ and $\cos^2 \phi + \sin^2 \phi = 1$. Then, after solving the integral in (32), we obtain

$$F_Z(z) = \frac{2z}{\xi} \left(\arcsin \left(\sqrt{\frac{u}{z}} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \sin \left(2 \arcsin \left(\sqrt{\frac{u}{z}} \right) \right) \right). \quad (33)$$

The function in (33) is inherently non-convex and highly non-linear due to the significant oscillations and fluctuations introduced by the trigonometric functions, leading to multiple local minima and maxima. This makes (33)

computationally expensive to analyze and optimize. Note, however, that

$$F_Z(z) \approx 1 - e^{-\frac{2z}{w}}, \text{ for } z \leq 200/\eta^2, \quad (34)$$

where $w = u + v$, which is a practical sensing range for a low-power IoTD (less than 5 meters [4], corresponding to $\delta \in [10^{-4}, 1]$). FIGURE 13 illustrates the accuracy of (12) for various values of u, v , and η , suggesting its suitability for reformulating the complexity of (2) into a more manageable form. ■

APPENDIX B. Proof of Non-Convexity of (15)

The first-order partial derivative of (15) is

$$\nabla_{\delta_j} \mathbb{E}(P_e(\boldsymbol{\delta})) = \frac{4\alpha \ln(\delta_j)}{w_j \delta_j} \left(\sum_{h=1}^{N-1} e^{-2 \sum_{i \neq h}^N \frac{\ln^2 \delta_i}{w_i}} - e^{-2 \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\ln^2 \delta_i}{w_i}} \right). \quad (35)$$

Note that this expression depends on the N variables, which means it is not constant. Therefore, we cannot conclude the convexity of the function based on the first-order conditions alone, and thus proceed to test the second-order condition. In this case, the Hessian matrix is given by

$$\mathcal{H} = \begin{bmatrix} h_{jj} & h_{jk} \\ h_{kj} & h_{kk} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (36)$$

where $k \neq j$, $h_{jj} = \nabla_{\delta_j}^2 \mathbb{E}(P_e)$, $h_{jk} = \nabla_{\delta_j \delta_k}^2 \mathbb{E}(P_e)$, $h_{kj} = \nabla_{\delta_k \delta_j}^2 \mathbb{E}(P_e)$, and $h_{kk} = \nabla_{\delta_k}^2 \mathbb{E}(P_e)$. Then, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} h_{jj} &= \frac{4\alpha}{w_j} \left(1 - \frac{\ln(\delta_j)}{\delta_j^2} \right) \left(\sum_{h=1}^{N-1} e^{-2 \sum_{i \neq h}^N \frac{\ln^2 \delta_i}{w_i}} - e^{-2 \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\ln^2 \delta_i}{w_i}} \right) + \dots \\ &\quad + \frac{16\alpha^2 \ln^2(\delta_j)}{w_j^2 \delta_j^2} e^{-2 \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\ln^2 \delta_i}{w_i}}, \end{aligned} \quad (37a)$$

$$h_{jk} = 16\alpha \left(\frac{\ln(\delta_j) \ln(\delta_k)}{\delta_j w_j w_k \delta_k} \right) \left(\sum_{h=1}^{N-2} e^{-2 \sum_{i \neq h}^N \frac{\ln^2 \delta_i}{w_i}} - e^{-2 \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\ln^2 \delta_i}{w_i}} \right). \quad (37b)$$

Similarly, h_{kk} is calculated by substituting δ_j and w_j in (37a) for δ_k and w_k , while h_{kj} can be calculated using (37b) by exchanging δ_k, w_k and δ_j, w_j . To determine convexity, let us evaluate the Hessian at some specific values, *e.g.*, $\delta_1 = 0.3$, $\delta_2 = 0.5$, and $N = 2$. Then, the eigenvalues of the matrix are negative, so the Hessian is not positive semi-definite, therefore the function is not convex in the range $[0, 1]$. ■

APPENDIX C. Closed-form for $\Pr(A_j|A_h)$

Using the cosine rule, we have

$$d_{i,j}^2 = d_{i,h}^2 + r_{j,h}^2 - 2d_{i,h}r_{j,h} \cos \varphi. \quad (38)$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr(A_j|A_h) &= \Pr(d_{i,j}^2 \leq \ln^2(\delta_j)/\eta^2 \mid d_{i,h}^2) \\ &= \Pr(d_{i,h}^2 + r_{j,h}^2 - 2d_{i,h}r_{j,h} \cos \varphi \leq \ln^2(\delta_j)/\eta^2), \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

where $d_{i,h}$ and $r_{j,h}$ are known. Therefore,

$$\Pr \left(\varphi \geq \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{d_{i,h}^2 + r_{j,h}^2 - \ln^2(\delta_j)/\eta^2}{2d_{i,h}r_{j,h}} \right) \right). \quad (40)$$

Let $r = \max(R, d_h^{(i)})$ and $R = \min(x_h, y_h, H - x_h, L - y_h)$. Herein, for $d_h^{(i)} \leq R$, φ has a PDF given by $1/(2\pi)$. However, for $d_h^{(i)} > R$, the PDF varies due to the corner effect in the rectangular area. Then, to calculate the PDF taking into account the corner effect, we divided the area in 8 equal octants, $k\pi/4 \leq \varphi < (k+1)\pi/4$, for $k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7\}$. Then, let us make a circumference with center at the expected position $(H/2, L/2)$. Focusing on the first octant, $0 \leq \varphi < \pi/4$, the part of the circumference with $0 \leq \varphi \leq \cos^{-1}(R/r)$ fall outside the network area $\xi = L \times H$. Then, this values of φ have zero occurrence probability. The same applies for the other 7 octants where R coincides with $\varphi = k\pi$, for $k \in \{0, 1/2, 1, 3/2\}$. Therefore, the PDF of φ within ξ given by

$$f(\varphi) = \begin{cases} 0, & k\pi - R/r < \varphi < k\pi + R/r, \\ \frac{1}{2\pi - 8 \cos^{-1}(R/r)}, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (41)$$

for $k \in \{0, 1/2, 1, 3/2\}$. Then, the CDF is calculated as

$$F_\varphi(a) = \int_0^a f(\varphi) d\varphi = \frac{a}{2\pi - 8 \cos^{-1}(R/r)}. \quad (42)$$

Then, $\Pr(\varphi \geq a)$ is equal to $1 - \Pr(\varphi < a)$. Herein, $\Pr(\varphi < a)$ can be calculated as $F_\varphi(a)$. Therefore, the conditional probability is given in closed-form as (19). ■

APPENDIX D. Benchmark solution for P2 (13)

We rewrite (13) assuming the equal- δ approach as follow

$$P2: \min_{\delta} F_Z(\ln^2(\delta)) \quad (43a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \mathbb{E}(P_e) \leq 0.1, \quad (43b)$$

where $\mathbb{E}(P_e)$ is given by

$$\mathbb{E}(P_e) = 1 - N(1 - e^{-\frac{21n^2(\delta)}{w}})e^{-\frac{21n^2(\delta)(N-1)}{w}}. \quad (44)$$

Note that minimizing $F_Z(\ln^2(\delta))$ is attained by maximizing δ . This is because F_Z is monotonically increasing in z and $z = \ln^2(\delta)$ is inversely proportional with respect to $\delta \in (0, 1]$. Therefore, the solution for P2 is given by

$$\delta^* = \sup \left\{ \delta : (1 - e^{-\frac{21n^2(\delta)}{w}})e^{-\frac{21n^2(\delta)(N-1)}{w}} \geq \frac{0.9}{N} \right\}, \quad (45)$$

where δ is calculated as the maximum value that satisfy the constraint in P2.

In scenarios where $N \rightarrow \infty$, as may occur in practical applications with very large N , an asymptotic solution emerges. In this case, the first term of (45) approaches 1, while the second term converges to 0 and becomes dominant.

As a result, we can simplify (45) by solely focusing on the second term as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \delta^* &= \sup \left\{ \delta : e^{-\frac{21n^2(\delta)(N-1)}{w}} \geq \frac{0.9}{N} \right\} \\ &= e \sqrt{\frac{w(\ln(N) - \ln(0.9))}{2(N-1)}}. \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

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